

OCULAR MANIFESTATION OF ANKYLOSING SPONDYLITIS: A LITERATURE REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

The present study intends to carry out a literature review on the ocular manifestations of ankylosing spondylitis, with the aim of analyzing the clinical repercussions and therapeutic management of the disease. The research was based on scientific articles in Portuguese and English published between 2010 and 2025, selected from scientific databases such as Pubmed and Scielo that were available in full. The results showed that ocular involvement in AS includes the sclera, episclera, uveal tract and other adjacent structures, including vitreous humor, retina, optic nerve and blood vessels.

Keywords: Ankylosing spondylitis. Uveitis. Inflammation.

INTRODUCTION

Ankylosing spondylitis (AS) is a chronic and progressive autoimmune disease. It is characterized mainly by involvement of the spine and sacroiliac joints, peripheral joints, fingers and entheses. Axial findings include spondylitis and sacroilitis. AS is characterized by inflammatory low back pain of insidious onset, lasting more than 3 months, morning stiffness lasting more than 30 minutes that improves with movement.

AS can affect other organs, such as the skin, eyes and cardiovascular system. The most common extra-articular manifestation is anterior uveitis, present in 40% of patients with a long history of the disease, usually related to positivity of the HLA-B27 marker. Approximately 30% of patients with AS also present extra-articular manifestations, including psoriasis, inflammatory bowel disease and acute anterior uveitis (AAU).

Uveitis can affect both ocular segments, with the anterior segment being most prevalently affected. It presents with sudden onset, recurrent and unilateral symptoms. Uveitis associated with AS is the most frequent ocular manifestation, with a prevalence of 30%.

OBJECTIVE

The present study aims to analyze scientific articles on the ocular manifestations of ankylosing spondylitis, its repercussions and therapeutic management.

METHODOLOGY

This study used an exploratory research method, through a bibliographic search to obtain references that expand knowledge about the ocular manifestations of ankylosing spondylitis. The research was based on scientific articles in Portuguese and English published between 2010 and 2025, selected from scientific databases such as Pubmed and SciELO that were available in full. For the search, health descriptors relevant to the topic were used, such as: Ankylosing spondylitis, Uveitis, Inflammation. The exclusion criteria refer to articles that exceeded the stipulated period of time and that are not available in full in the databases searched.

RESULTS

Uveitis can affect both ocular segments, with the anterior segment being most prevalently affected. It presents with sudden onset, recurrent and unilateral symptoms. Uveitis associated with AS is the most frequent ocular manifestation, with a prevalence of 30%.

Ocular involvement of AS includes the sclera, episclera, uveal tract, and other adjacent structures, including the vitreous humor, retina, optic nerve, and blood vessels. Its characteristic feature is the “ping-pong” pattern, which means that uveitis can alternately affect the eyes.

HLA-B27-associated anterior uveitis presents with inflammation restricted to the uvea (middle vascular layer of the eye). HLA-B27-associated anterior uveitis presents with

inflammation restricted to the uvea (middle vascular layer of the eye). Current evidence suggests that HLA-B27-positive UAA has a less favorable prognosis and is prone to frequent relapses.

Blurred vision is the main symptom of UAA caused by ciliary spasm and the presence of cells and/or enlargement in the anterior chamber of the eye; pain, redness and tearing are the other main symptoms.⁴ Episodes of photophobia and keratic precipitates, hypopyon, pupillary membrane and hyphema are also part of the clinical picture.⁵ The most common ocular complications were cataract (9.7%) and glaucoma (4.8%). The clinical evaluation of the ophthalmologist is of utmost importance in establishing the diagnosis of the patient with uveitis.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

In cases of chronic disease progression, there are high rates of complications, such as seclusion, pupillary occlusion, low visual acuity, cataracts, secondary glaucoma, cystoid macular edema, macular hole and folding of the internal limiting membrane of the retina in the macular area, especially in patients with positive HLA-B27.

Regarding therapy in the management of uveitis, topical corticosteroids play an important role in the acute phase of ocular manifestation, but their chronic use is associated with a greater chance of complications such as secondary glaucoma, cataracts and iris atrophy.

Systemic NSAIDs inhibit prostaglandins and are used in mild conditions and inflammations that do not respond to topical therapy.¹¹ They have been found to be an ideal alternative to glucocorticoids and are able to reduce uveitis attacks.¹¹ Conventional synthetic disease-modifying antirheumatic drugs (DMARDs) such as methotrexate have demonstrated efficacy in idiopathic uveitis or uveitis associated with other conditions.

Biological therapy is also widely used in more severe cases. The pro-inflammatory cytokine tumor necrosis factor alpha is very important in treatment, because high levels of this cytokine have been found in the aqueous humor and inflamed joints of patients with AS. TNF alpha inhibitors, such as infliximab and adalimumab, are very safe and effective alternatives.

REFERENCES

- Wenker KJ, Quint JM. Ankylosing Spondylitis. 2023 Jun 20. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2023 Jan-. PMID: 29261996.

- Al-ghamdi AA. Eye and Rheumatology. 2021 Jan 6. In: Almoallim H, Cheikh M, editors. Skills in Rheumatology [Internet]. Singapore: Springer; 2021. Chapter 19. PMID: 36315796.
- Parameswaran P, Lucke M. HLA-B27 Syndromes. 2023 Jul 4. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2023 Jan-. PMID: 31855367.
- Pandey A, Ravindran V. Ocular Manifestations of Spondyloarthritis. *Mediterr J Rheumatol*. 2023 Mar 31;34(1):24-29. doi: 10.31138/mjr.34.1.24. PMID: 37223599; PMCID: PMC10201097.
- Kemeny-Beke A, Szodoray P. Ocular manifestations of rheumatic diseases. *Int Ophthalmol*. 2020 Feb;40(2):503-510. doi: 10.1007/s10792-019-01183-9. Epub 2019 Oct 3. PMID: 31583550.
- Lussari L. MC, Queiroz B. G., Silva V. HV da, Pereira H. J. de O., & Mota L. OD (2022). Late diagnosis of ankylosing spondylitis from anterior uveitis: case report. *Electronic Journal of Medical Archives*, 13, e10518. <https://doi.org/10.25248/reamed.e10518.2022>
- Dimantas MAP, Lowder C, Muccioli C. Anterior uveitis associated with systemic diseases. *Arq Bras Oftalmol* [Internet]. 2003;66(2):235–8. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1590/S0004-27492003000200023>
- Duarte AP, Marques CD, Bortoluzzo AB, Gonçalves CR, Silva JAB da, Ximenes AC, et al.. Epidemiological profile of juvenile-onset spondyloarthritis compared with adult-onset spondyloarthritis in a large Brazilian cohort. *Rev Bras Reumatol* [Internet]. 2014Nov;54(6):424–30. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rbr.2014.06.005>
- Vale IMS, Pereira IA, Mastella M de S. Analysis of the frequency of uveitis in patients with spondyloarthritis, its complications and association with clinical parameters of the disease. *Rev brasoftalmol* [Internet]. 2018Mar;77(2):80–4. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.5935/0034-7280.20180017>
- Vale IMS, Pereira IA, Mastella M de S. Analysis of the frequency of uveitis in patients with spondyloarthritis, its complications and association with clinical parameters of the disease. *Rev brasoftalmol* [Internet]. 2018Mar;77(2):80–4. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.5935/0034-7280.20180017>
- Sampaio-Barros PD, Keiserman M, Meirelles E de S, Pinheiro M de M, Ximenes AC, Azevedo VF, et al.. Recommendations on diagnosis and treatment of ankylosing spondylitis. *Rev Bras Reumatol* [Internet]. 2013May;53(3):242–57. Available from: <https://www.scielo.br/j/rbr/a/Y6T9QFnrh5wTFhLVhv8MSmd/>
- Huang T, Pu Y, Wang X, Li Y, Yang H, Luo Y, Liu Y. Metabolomic analysis in spondyloarthritis: A systematic review. *Front Microbiol*. 2022 Sep 2;13:965709. doi: 10.3389/fmicb.2022.965709. Erratum in: *Front Microbiol*. 2022 Dec 12;13:1100290. PMID: 36118235; PMCID: PMC9479008.
13. Gouveia EB, Elmann D, Morales MS de Á. Ankylosing spondylitis and uveitis: review. *Rev Bras Reumatol* [Internet]. 2012Sep;52(5):749–56. Available from: <https://www.scielo.br/j/rbr/a/ZV5Yt6qT494D6LM8VHZxrJn/>

van der Horst-Bruinsma I, van Bentum R, Verbraak FD, Rath T, Rosenbaum JT, Misterska-Skora M, Hoepken B, Irvin-Sellers O, VanLunen B, Bauer L, Rudwaleit M. The impact of Certolizumab pegol treatment on the incidence of anterior uveitis flares in patients with axial spondyloarthritis: 48-week interim results from C-VIEW. *RMD Open*. 2020 Apr;6(1):e001161. doi: 10.1136/rmdopen-2019-001161. PMID: 32371433; PMCID: PMC7299504.